

IRIS Carbon Mapping Project

Final Report and Outline Delivery Roadmap

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1 Abstract

IRIS, the eInfrastructure for Research and Innovation for STFC, is bound by the UKRI commitment to become Net Zero by 2030.

To achieve Net Zero one must:

- Model a systems carbon emission's.
- Measure the things needed to evaluate that model;
- Monitor on an ongoing basis the modelled emissions; and
- Moderate carbon emissions by making decisions informed by the monitoring.

This report presents four models covering both batch and cloud clusters providing both storage and compute services. The models apportion carbon costs to users and to service providers for both scope 2 and scope 3 carbon emissions.

The ability to use these models in practise has been demonstrated by running them on sample monitoring data from IRIS service providers. Simple and enhanced models are compared showing little to choose between them at this early stage of IRIS's Net Zero journey.

IRIS constituents were consulted on their carbon reporting requirements and there are presented here. The key issues affecting the IRIS Net Zero journey are discussed and an outline roadmap is presented. Recommended actions include actions to regularly measure and monitor the modelled carbon emission with the intention to drive changes leading to reduced carbon emissions.

Table of Contents

1	ABSTRACT	1
2	INTRODUCTION	3
3	CARBON MODELS	4
3.1	SIMPLE APPORTIONMENT MODEL FOR PAYLOADS	5
3.2	ENHANCED APPORTIONMENT MODEL FOR PAYLOADS.....	6
3.3	SIMPLE APPORTIONMENT MODEL FOR STORAGE.....	8
3.4	ENHANCED MODEL FOR STORAGE	9
3.5	MODEL SUMMARY	9
3.5.1	<i>Simple Payload Model Summary & Inputs</i>	10
3.5.2	<i>Enhanced Payload Model Summary & Inputs</i>	11
3.5.3	<i>Simple Storage Model Summary & Inputs</i>	12
3.5.4	<i>Enhanced Storage Model Summary & Inputs</i>	13
4	APPLYING MODELS TO REAL DATA	14
4.1	APPLYING MODELS TO QMUL GRIDPP T2 BATCH DATA.....	14
4.2	APPLYING STORAGE MODELS TO LUSTRE STORAGE	16
4.3	APPLYING MODELS STFC CLOUD DATA	17
4.4	MODEL COMPARISON	18
5	IRIS NETZERO REPORTING REQUIREMENTS	20
5.1	IRIS FEDERATION REPORTING PERSPECTIVES	20
5.2	IRIS PROVIDERS REPORTING PERSPECTIVES	20
5.3	IRIS USERS REPORTING PERSPECTIVES	21
6	OUTLINE DELIVERY ROADMAP	22
6.1	CONTEXT	22
6.2	TACKLING THE NETZERO PROBLEM.....	23
6.3	IRIS NETZERO ACTIONS	25
7	CONCLUSION	27
8	ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	27

2 Introduction

In 2019 the UK parliament declared an environment and climate emergency and the UK became the world's first major economy to adopt a legally binding target to reduce its greenhouse gas emissions to net zero by 2050¹. As a result, UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) has committed to becoming Carbon Net Zero by 2040 this includes its Digital Research Infrastructure² which encompasses IRIS interests.

To achieve Net Zero one must:

- Model a systems carbon emissions.
- Measure the things needed to evaluate that model;
- Monitor on an ongoing basis the modelled emissions; and
- Moderate carbon emissions by making decisions informed by the monitoring.

To enable this carbon monitoring, IRIS will need to develop carbon accounting methods to allocate facility carbon costs to carbon cost centres. This small IRIS Carbon Mapping Project (IRIS-CMP) has in 5 months developed models to allocate facility carbon costs to IRIS payloads in both batch and cloud payloads. We also present an outline a delivery roadmap for future carbon reporting within IRIS.

IRIS-CMP identified the following objectives:

- organise two face to face meetings to engage partners and discuss reporting requirements and models & measurements;
- develop carbon models to allocate carbon costs to payloads;
- report the findings and develop an outline delivery roadmap.

To discuss carbon costs some definitions are useful. Carbon emissions are classified into scopes:

- Scope 1 emissions are essentially caused by burning fossil fuels directly which in the IRIS context would only pertain to emissions of data centre diesel backup generators.
- Scope 2 emissions are the additional emissions caused due to current operations. We sometimes refer to scope 2 emissions as the active carbon costs. In the IRIS context this will be the carbon emissions due to the electricity used to run the datacentres.
- Scope 3 emissions are those due to setting up and decommissioning operations. We sometimes refer to scope 3 emissions as embedded or embodied carbon costs. In the IRIS context scope 3 encompasses emissions due to building data centres, manufacturing and delivering computer and network systems and additionally emissions due to decommissioning/disposal.

¹ <https://www.gov.uk/government/news/uk-becomes-first-major-economy-to-pass-net-zero-emissions-law>

² <https://net-zero-dri.ceda.ac.uk>

3 Carbon Models

IRIS-CMP takes an apportionment approach to modelling carbon emissions. This is essentially an accounting approach where the total carbon cost is well known and apportioned to carbon cost centres. The apportionment approach was chosen as it should be relatively straight forward to implement and gives the big picture.

To assess the quality of a model one can consider the following questions.

- Is it practical to implement the model?
- Does the model give robust results?
- Does the model encourage user behaviour that tends to moderate carbon emissions?
- Does the model encourage the resource provider to operate in a way that tends to moderate carbon emissions?

The modelling work undertaken by the IRISCAST project³ shows that for scope 2 active emissions we can essentially work in terms of energy consumed and then convert to carbon equivalent emissions by multiplying the electrical energy usage by the carbon intensity of the electricity consumed. This can be written as follows where C_{ax}^t is the active carbon for item x in a time period t , E_x^t is the energy used by item x in the time period t and I^t is the prevailing carbon intensity of the electricity used at time t .

$$C_{ax}^t = E_x^t \times I^t$$

When working with scope 3 embedded emissions we do not have this option of working in units of energy and must work directly in terms of carbon equivalent emissions. With embedded carbon we often want to amortise an item's embedded carbon cost over the lifetime of that item. This can be written as follows where C_{ex}^t is the embedded carbon cost for item x apportioned to time period of interest t , C_{ex} is the total scope 3 embedded carbon for the item and T_x is the expected lifetime of the item.

$$C_{ex}^t = C_{ex} \cdot \frac{t}{T_x}$$

To obtain the total carbon cost associated with operating an item in a period t written as C_x^t we can simply sum the active and apportioned embedded carbon as follows.

$$C_x^t = C_{ax}^t + C_{ex}^t$$

Due to the short timeframe of this IRIS-CMP project and the additional complexity in addressing GPU or other accelerator-based workloads it was decided that these were out of scope.

What follows are two models for cluster payloads and two models for cluster storage, as different approaches are needed in each case.

³ IRISCAST Final Report: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7692451>

3.1 Simple Apportionment Model for Payloads

This simple model assumes that a batch or cloud resource does not over-commit resources. The term resource allocation unit is used to describe either a CPU core (or CPU thread if hyper-threading is enabled) in the batch environment, or CPU core mapped to a virtual CPU core in the cloud environment.

The term payload is used to describe either a batch job, in a batch environment, or a virtual machine (VM) in a cloud environment. It is assumed that payloads reserve and can only use a fixed number of resource allocation units during their run time.

Given that one can measure or make a good estimate of the total facility energy usage E_f^t in a period t , then this can be apportioned to a payload p as follows,

$$E_p = E_f^t \cdot \frac{R_p}{R_f} \cdot \frac{t_p}{t}$$

where E_p is the energy apportioned to a payload, R_p are the number of resource allocation units used by that payload, R_f is the total number of resource allocation units available at the facility, t_p is the wall clock time taken for the payload to run.

From this E_p the scope 2 active carbon cost for the payload p can be calculated as

$$C_{ap} = E_p \cdot I^t$$

It should be noted that unallocated payload slots, withing an accounting period t , will still have a carbon cost to them and that can notionally be calculated in energy terms as:

$$E_{idle}^t = E_f^t \cdot \frac{R_{idle}}{R_f} \cdot \frac{t_{idle}}{t}$$

Where R_{idle} is the number of idle resource allocation units and t_{idle} is the time period over which those resource allocation units were idle.

However, this can more practically be calculated in energy terms simply as the difference between the total energy used by the facility and the sum of the energy apportioned to the payloads p :

$$E_{idle}^t = E_f^t - \sum_{p=1}^{payloads} E_p$$

From this the scope 2 active carbon cost attributable to the facility, as opposed to user payloads, can be calculated as:

$$C_{a\ idle} = E_{idle}^t \times I^t$$

To deal with the scope 3 embedded carbon costs requires providers to keep an inventory of items that comprise their service or facility. This inventory needs to include the scope 3 embedded carbon cost of the item and the expected lifetime such that the amortisation described earlier can be accomplished. The ‘‘birth date’’ of the item should also be recorded.

Given that such an inventory is in place then an embedded carbon cost rate Q_{ef} for the facility can be calculated as:

$$Q_{ef} = \sum_{x=1}^{items} \frac{C_{ex}}{T_x}$$

And therefore, the facility embedded carbon costs can be apportioned to payloads p as:

$$C_{ep} = \frac{R_p}{R_f} \cdot t_p \cdot Q_{ef}$$

And the embedded carbon cost allocated to unallocated payload resource allocation units:

$$C_{e\ idle}^t = t \cdot Q_{ef} - \left(\sum_{p=1}^{payloads} C_{ep} \right)$$

As discussed earlier summing the active and embedded (scope 2 and 3) allocations for a payload or idle then yield the total carbon cost.

3.2 Enhanced Apportionment Model for Payloads

The simple model above used the total payload duration t_p also referred to as the real time or wall clock time. Another common payload statistic is the CPU time. This is the time that the payload is actively running on the CPU, the rest of the time the payload may be idle waiting for network, storage or memory access for example. Since we have this additional information more detailed models are possible.

The enhanced model discussed in this section assumes the idle power of a facility is constant. This would need to be monitored in practice and adjustments to the model made if it was found to vary significantly over time.

This enhanced payload model is represented graphically in Figure 1. The dark grey area represents the baseload energy used by the payload due to the idle power of the machine while the light grey area represents the energy used by the payload due to the CPU actively working. The CPU time is represented by the sum of the time dimensions of the light grey areas and is denoted as t^{CPU} . The height of the light grey areas (D) represents the active power we denote below as P_{slot}^{CPU} , while the height of the dark grey area (E) represents the idle power which for an individual payload is simply the apportionment of the facility idle power P_f^{idle} .

Therefore, this model relies on a measurement or estimate of the idle power of the facility. This could be achieved by taking direct power measurements of the cluster when it is unloaded and idle during commissioning or maintenance windows. Alternatively extrapolating power usage against cluster load back to zero load could give an estimate of the idle power.

Figure 1: Sketch graph of payload power using idle-power for the full duration 'Realtime' in dark grey and in light grey the same payload using active power in three bursts for a total of 'CPUTime'. The sum of grey areas gives the total energy. The height of the dark grey area (E) represents the idle power while the height of the light grey area (D) represents the active power.

Given that a suitable idle power P_f^{idle} can be determined then this model asserts that the difference between the measured energy consumption for the entire facility E_f^t in a period t and the energy attributable to the idle power over that same period must be due to CPU activity. Thus, the energy used by the facility in a period t due to CPU activity which we will term $E_{f\ CPU}^t$ can be expressed as:

$$E_{f\ CPU}^t = E_f^t - P_f^{idle} \cdot t$$

This model asserts that $E_{f\ CPU}^t$ is attributable to the light grey areas of the figure above. Which we can write as:

$$E_{f\ CPU}^t = \sum_{p=1}^{payloads} (P_{slot}^{CPU} \cdot t_p^{CPU})$$

And simplify to:

$$E_{f\ CPU}^t = P_{slot}^{CPU} \cdot \sum_{p=1}^{payloads} (t_p^{CPU})$$

$$E_{f\ CPU}^t = P_{slot}^{CPU} \cdot t_f^{CPU}$$

Therefore:

$$E_{f\ CPU}^t = E_f^t - P_f^{idle} \cdot t = P_{slot}^{CPU} \cdot t_f^{CPU}$$

Which lets us calculate the active power for a resource allocation unit P_{slot}^{CPU} as:

$$P_{slot}^{CPU} = \frac{E_f^t - P_f^{idle} \cdot t}{t_f^{CPU}}$$

Given that we can easily calculate the P_{slot}^{CPU} from facility level figures we can then work out the energy consumed by a payload due to the CPU doing active work E_p^{CPU} and the idle energy of a payload E_p^{idle} .

$$E_p^{CPU} = P_{slot}^{CPU} \cdot t_p^{CPU}$$

$$E_p^{idle} = P_f^{idle} \cdot \frac{R_p}{R_f} \cdot t_p$$

These are then summed to give the total energy of a payload E_p :

$$E_p = E_p^{idle} + E_p^{CPU}$$

$$E_p = P_f^{idle} \cdot \frac{R_p}{R_f} \cdot t_p + P_{slot}^{CPU} \cdot t_p^{CPU}$$

As in the simple apportionment model for payloads the unallocated resource allocation units must account for the remaining facility energy usage and are calculated in the same way as before. Similarly, the scope 3 embedded costs can be apportioned as per the simple apportionment model.

3.3 Simple Apportionment Model for Storage

Storage clusters need a different approach to the payload approaches discussed earlier. Assuming that a storage cluster does not overcommit its capacity then a simple apportionment based on user storage allocations (quotas) can be applied.

The scope 2 carbon costs in energy terms can be expressed as:

$$E_{s\ user}^t = \frac{S_{user}}{S_{total}} \cdot E_s^t$$

Where, for a time period t , E_s^t is the total energy usage of the storage sub-system, S_{user} is the storage capacity allocated to the user or project, S_{total} is the total capacity of the allocatable storage and $E_{s\ user}^t$ is the energy usage apportioned to that user or project.

To address scope 3 emissions then a storage carbon inventory will be required which can be used to calculate an embedded carbon cost rate Q_{es} for the storage system as:

$$Q_{es} = \sum_{x=1}^{storage_items} \frac{C_{ex}}{T_x}$$

The scope 3 embedded costs for an accounting period t can also be apportioned by the allocated storage capacity to a user or project as:

$$C_{e\ s\ user}^t = \frac{S_{user}}{S_{Total}} \cdot t \cdot Q_{es}$$

3.4 Enhanced Model for Storage

The simple model ignores access to the storage. To take an extreme example tape storage uses no energy when data is at rest on an idle tape, but energy is clearly needed to read and write to the tape. To varying degrees this is also true of magnetic disk and solid state flash storage technologies. To take this into account the user access to the storage can be included into the model as follows.

A more complex scope 2 model for storage sub-systems could allocate the base load by user capacity allocation as above, but then energy usage above the base load could be allocated by bytes read or written.

This approach assumes that the idle power for the storage sub-system can be estimated or measured as P_s^{idle} and that P_s^{idle} remains constant. Given that then in a period t the baseload energy can be written as $P_s^{idle} \cdot t$ and apportioned to users or projects by allocated storage capacity as in the simple scheme earlier. The difference between the baseload and the total energy used by the storage in the same period E_s^t can then be attributed to user access of the storage, and hence apportioned to users by bytes read or written B .

This can be written as:

$$E_{s\ user}^t = \frac{S_{user}}{S_{total}} \cdot P_s^{idle} \cdot t + (E_s^t - P_s^{idle} \cdot t) \frac{B_{user}}{\sum_{u=1}^{all\ users} B_u}$$

The scope 3 carbon can be allocated as in the simple storage model.

It is not clear if it is practical to measure data access for all kinds of storage which may limit this model's applicability.

3.5 Model Summary

What follows is a summary of each of the models discussed and a list of the needed inputs. The payload models and the storage models assume pure compute/cloud resources and pure storage resources. A real cluster will likely comprise a storage sub-cluster and a compute sub-cluster in this case the relevant model can be applied to each sub-cluster and totalled to give a more realistic model of the mixed cluster.

3.5.1 Simple Payload Model Summary & Inputs

	Scope 2 – Energy	Scope 3 – Carbon
Payload	$E_p = E_f^t \cdot \frac{R_p}{R_f} \cdot \frac{t_p}{t}$	$C_{ep} = \frac{R_p}{R_f} \cdot t_p \cdot Q_{ef}$ <p>Where:</p> $Q_{ef} = \sum_{x=1}^{items} \frac{C_{ex}}{T_x}$
Idle	$E_{idle}^t = E_f^t - \sum_{p=1}^{payloads} E_p$	$C_{e\ idle}^t = t \cdot Q_{ef} - \left(\sum_{p=1}^{payloads} C_{ep} \right)$

Table 1: Summary of the Simple Payload Model showing allocations of Scope 2 energy and Scope 3 carbon to user payloads and the remaining idle allocation to the provider.

Input	Description
E_f^t	Facility Energy usage over an accounting period (including cooling) could be estimated from PDU readings multiplied by PUE
t	Duration of accounting period
t_p	Elapsed time of a payload (Wall clock)
R_p	Resource slots allocated to job (eg CPU's)
R_f	Total slots available at facility
C_{ex}	Inventory Entry: Embedded carbon of each item x in facility
T_x	Inventory Entry: expected lifetime of each item x in facility

Table 2: Summary of the inputs needed to evaluate the Simple Payload Model.

3.5.2 Enhanced Payload Model Summary & Inputs

	Scope 2 - Energy	Scope 3 - Carbon
Payload	$E_p = P_f^{idle} \cdot \frac{R_p}{R_f} \cdot t_p + P_{slot}^{CPU} \cdot t_p^{CPU}$ <p>Where:</p> $P_{slot}^{CPU} = \frac{E_f^t - P_f^{idle} \cdot t}{t_f^{CPU}}$	$C_{ep} = \frac{R_p}{R_f} \cdot t_p \cdot Q_{ef}$ <p>Where:</p> $Q_{ef} = \sum_{x=1}^{items} \frac{C_{ex}}{T_x}$
Idle	$E_{idle}^t = E_f^t - \sum_{p=1}^{payloads} E_p$	$C_{e\ idle}^t = t \cdot Q_{ef} - \left(\sum_{p=1}^{payloads} C_{ep} \right)$

Table 3: Summary of the Enhanced Payload Model showing allocations of Scope 2 energy and Scope 3 carbon to user payloads and the remaining idle allocation to the provider

Input	Description
E_f^t	Facility Energy usage over an accounting period (including cooling) could be estimated from PDU readings multiplied by PUE
P_f^{idle}	Idle power draw of the facility (including cooling) could be estimated from PDU readings during an idle period multiplied by PUE
t	Duration of accounting period
t_f^{CPU}	Total CPUtime delivered by the facility during the accounting period.
t_p	Elapsed time of a payload (Wall clock)
t_p^{CPU}	CPUtime of a payload
R_p	Resource slots allocated to job (eg CPU's)
R_f	Total slots available at facility
C_{ex}	Inventory Entry: Embedded carbon of each item x in facility
T_x	Inventory Entry: expected lifetime of each item x in facility

Table 4: Summary of the inputs needed to evaluate the Enhanced Payload Model.

3.5.3 Simple Storage Model Summary & Inputs

Scope 2 - Energy	$E_{s\ user}^t = \frac{S_{user}}{S_{Total}} \cdot E_s^t$
Scope 3 - Carbon	<p>Where:</p> $C_{e\ s\ user}^t = \frac{S_{user}}{S_{Total}} \cdot t \cdot Q_{es}$ $Q_{es} = \sum_{x=1}^{storage_items} \frac{C_{ex}}{T_x}$

Table 5: Summary of the Simple Storage Model showing allocations of Scope 2 energy and Scope 3 carbon to user storage use and the remaining allocation to the provider.

Input	Description
E_s^t	Storage Energy usage over an accounting period (including cooling) could be estimated from PDU readings multiplied by PUE
S_{user}	Storage capacity allocated to a user
S_{total}	Total storage capacity of the storage subsystem
t	Duration of accounting period
C_{ex}	Inventory Entry: Embedded carbon of each storage item x
T_x	Inventory Entry: expected lifetime of each storage item x

Table 6: Summary of the inputs needed to evaluate the Simple Storage Model.

3.5.4 Enhanced Storage Model Summary & Inputs

Scope 2 - Energy	$E_{s\ user}^t = \frac{S_{user}}{S_{total}} \cdot P_s^{idle} \cdot t + (E_s^t - P_s^{idle} \cdot t) \frac{B_{user}}{\sum_{u=1}^{all_users} B_u}$
Scope 3 - Carbon	<p style="text-align: center;">Where:</p> $C_{e\ s\ user}^t = \frac{S_{user}}{S_{Total}} \cdot t \cdot Q_{es}$ $Q_{es} = \sum_{x=1}^{storage\ items} \frac{C_{ex}}{T_x}$

Table 7: Summary of the Enhanced Storage Model showing allocations of Scope 2 energy and Scope 3 carbon to user storage use and the remaining allocation to the provider.

Input	Description
E_s^t	Storage Energy usage over an accounting period (including cooling) could be estimated from PDU readings multiplied by PUE
P_s^{idle}	Idle power draw of the storage cluster (including cooling) could be estimated from PDU readings during an idle period multiplied by PUE.
S_{user}	Storage capacity allocated to a user
S_{total}	Total Storage capacity of the storage subsystem
t	Duration of accounting period
B_{user}	Bytes read from, or written to, a users storage area
C_{ex}	Inventory Entry: Embedded carbon of each storage item x
T_x	Inventory Entry: expected lifetime of each storage item x

Table 8: Summary of the inputs needed to evaluate the Enhanced Storage Model.

4 Applying Models to Real Data

To test that the models from section 3 are practical to implement monitoring and accounting data were collected and used to evaluate the models.

Data were collected from the QMUL GridPP T2 cluster and from the SCD STFC Cloud service. These were selected to be a typical IRIS batch queue cluster and typical cloud resource respectively.

On the QMUL GridPP T2 cluster Energy usage was collected using IPMI⁴ and rack Power Distribution Units (PDU's) via SNMP⁵ and job data were collected by the SLURM⁶ scheduler's accounting system. Four racks of compute nodes were selected to provide sample data over a 24 hour period. The racks contained 120 *Dell PowerEdge R640* compute nodes with 96 cpu threads each. The racks also contained a total of four *Mellanox SN2410* switches, all of which were supplied with power and metered by 12 *APC APDU9953* PDU's.

The SCD STFC Cloud service is run on OpenStack⁷ monitored by the Prometheus⁸ monitoring suite. Following a face to face meeting with the SCD Cloud team on March 26th 2024 sample data were extracted for 85 hypervisor nodes, forming a subset of the entire cloud service.

4.1 Applying Models to QMUL GridPP T2 Batch Data

Data collection was conducted over a 24 hour period for the four racks of identical compute nodes and was processed through both the simple and enhanced payload models. To evaluate the enhanced model an estimate of the idle power was needed. For operational reasons it was not possible to take machines out of service to get a measured idle power so an estimate was made using the data that was available.

The idle power was obtained by fitting and extrapolating the data as shown in Figure 2. For each minute the combined IPMI and Slurm data told us the node power draw for each node (P_N) and the number of CPU's in that node allocated to jobs (N_{CA}). For each discrete value of N_{CA} the mean and standard deviation of the measured node powers P_N are plotted against the allocated CPU count (N_{CA}) as show by the blue dots and error bars in Figure 2. The orange line is the empirical fit $P_N(N_{CA}) = (P_{full} - P_{idle}) \times [1 - \exp(-C \times N_{CA})] + P_{idle}$, where P_{full} is the power of the node at full load, P_{idle} the idle power, and C a fitting coefficient. Extrapolating back to an allocated CPU count of zero, the orange line on the plot, shows us the idle power for a node P_{idle} is 137.1W. As the four racks in question contain 120 identical nodes this gives an estimate for P_f^{idle} of 16.45 kWh. This estimate has a number of short comings but is sufficient for testing the practical application of the model. It would be preferable to make a direct idle power measurement but this was not operationally possible.

⁴ IPMI is the Intelligent Platform Management Interface, a protocol for querying hardware information from a servers basebord management controller (BMC).

⁵ SNMP is the Simple Network Management Protocol, used for querying data from network devices.

⁶ SLURM is an open source cluster workload manager: <https://github.com/SchedMD/slurm>

⁷ OpenStack an open source cloud software infrastructure: <https://www.openstack.org>

⁸ Prometheus is an open source monitoring framework: <https://prometheus.io>

Figure 2: Node power P_N as a function of allocated CPU cores in a node N_{CA} . The Blue dots and error bars show the mean power and std-deviation for each discrete N_{CA} . Regression line y-intercept gives the idle power of a node $P_{idle} \approx 137.1W$.

Input	Value	Slurm name	Description
E_f^t	1597 kWh	-	Facility Energy usage. In this four rack example the PDU cumulative energy readings were used to calculate this.
p_f^{idle}	16.45 kW	-	Idle power draw of the facility. In this example the 137.1W per node was multiplied by 120 nodes.
t	86400 s	-	Duration of accounting period. In this case 24 hours.
t_f^{CPU}	-	$\sum TotalCPU$	Total CPUtime delivered by the facility during the accounting period. Sum of the TotalCPU figures for all payloads
t_p	-	Elapsed	Elapsed time of a payload (Wall clock)
t_p^{CPU}	-	TotalCPU	CPUtime of a payload
$Slots_p$	-	AllocCPUS	Resource slots allocated to job (eg CPU's)
$Slots_f$	11520	-	Total slots available at facility. In this case 120 nodes with 96 cores each.

Table 9: Measured and derived constants and Slurm accounting data names used to evaluate the payload models for QMUL batch payloads.

User	Simple Payload Model	Enhanced Payload Model
	kWh	kWh
prdatl	1204.79	1191.95
pillhcb	159.08	242.24
pilcms	76.83	71.28
pilat1	48.86	51.58
Pilmoe	10.75	16.86
Pildune	2.46	0.61
Others	0.08	0.04
Sub total	1502.86	1574.57
Idle(provider)	94.14	22.43
Total	1597	1597

Table 10: Results of evaluating the Simple and Enhanced Payload models on QMUL batch payloads the 24 hour period of 2024-03-07.

Well defined values of the Scope 3 equipment carbon costs and expected lifetimes were not available and so the model to apportion embedded carbon costs was not exercised in this instance. Establishment of a reliable inventory of embedded carbon costs is an action item that comes out of this IRIS-CMP work.

4.2 Applying Storage Models to Lustre Storage

Storage access data for the Lustre filesystem at QMUL was unavailable which ruled out demonstrating the enhanced storage model. Automated measurements from all the rack PDU's could not be implemented in time for this work so rough power measurements were taken manually on one rack of storage equipment which was used to estimate the entire storage power draw. With these rough power measurements and accurate quota allocations the Simple Storage Model was evaluated as shown in Table 11 and Table 12.

Input	Value	Description
E_s^t	768 kWh	Storage Energy usage over an accounting period. In this example 5 racks of storage drawing 6.4kW/rack for 24 hours.
S_{user}	-	Storage capacity allocated to a user
S_{Total}	15 PB	Total Storage capacity of the storage subsystem
t	86400 s	Duration of accounting period

Table 11: Measurements, constants and settings used to evaluate the Simple Storage model.

User/group	Quota	kWh
atlas	11500	588.8
dune	1100	56.3
belle	1000	51.2
lhcb	300	15.4
t2k.org	250	12.8
fermilab	200	10.2
other	200	10.2
Unallocated	450	23.0
Total	15000	768.0

Table 12: Results of evaluating the Simple Storage Model on QMUL data for the 24 hour period of 2024-03-27

4.3 Applying Models STFC Cloud Data

Following a face to face meeting with the SCD Cloud team on March 26th 2024 the models were discussed with the SCD Cloud team and they were highly confident that their Prometheus monitoring will be able to collect the data needed to evaluate the simple payload and storage models and the enhanced payload model. They were also quite confident that they could collect data for the enhanced storage model.

Sample SCD Cloud data was collected for the first 20 hours of 27th March 2024. The supplied data did not cover all input quantities for all models. Sufficient data was available to evaluate the simple payload model. For 85 cloud nodes, we were able to integrate the 2-hourly average power measurements to obtain E_f^t .

Input	Value	Prometheus name	Description
E_f^t	424.26 kWh	-	Facility Energy usage, derived from “node_hwmon_power_average_watt” and our accounting period t on all nodes.
t	72000 seconds	-	Duration of accounting period. In this case 20 hours.
t_p	-	-	Elapsed time of a VM (Wall clock) during our accounting period, as inferred by the VM’s “launched_at” and “terminated_at” time from OpenStack.
R_p	-	openstack_nova_vcpus_used	Resource slots allocated to VM (eg CPU’s)
R_f	?	openstack_nova_vcpus_available	Total slots available at facility. In this case number of all vcpus on all the nodes.

Table 13: Measured and derived constants and Prometheus accounting data names used to evaluate the simple payload model for STFC Cloud payloads.

User	Simple Payload Model
	kWh
Project 1	51.51
Project 2	31.52
Project 3	25.07
Project 4	18.22
Project 5	17.61
Project 6	12.89
Others	94.00
Sub total	250.82
Idle(provider)	173.44
Total	424.26

Table 14: Results of evaluating the Simple and Payload models on data from SCD STFC Cloud for the first 20 hours of 2024-03-27.

4.4 Model Comparison

Having developed two allocation models a choice of which to use must be made.

Figure 3 below helps to explain the behaviour of the two models. The graph shows, on a log scale, the energy allocated by each model to perform a fixed amount of work (defined as 1 CPU second) for jobs of different efficiency (essentially the ratio of CPU to wall clock time). Both models slope down to the right showing that both models motivate users to employ more efficient code. In the high efficiency regime, where well behaved jobs can generally be assumed to fall, then the enhanced model allocates more of the energy to user jobs and thus there is a smaller residual allocated to the provider than if the simple model was used. As the compute clusters only exist to serve users then it can be argued that as much of the energy usage as is reasonable be allocated to the users. However it must be noted that the graph is plotted on a log scale so the difference between the simple and enhanced models in this high efficiency regime, though noticeable, is small.

Figure 3: Behaviour of the Simple and Enhanced payload models for a fixed amount of work (constant CPUtime) varying with Job Efficiency. Plotted on a log scale.

When choosing a model practicalities must also be considered. The enhanced model requires an idle power measurement/estimate which adds operational complexity to using the model. The enhanced model also requires CPU time as well as elapsed time which may not be so readily available from providers without some effort.

Bringing this all together it is envisaged that any provider could implement the simple model, and with a little effort any provider could implement the enhanced model which is arguably fairer. Pragmatically IRIS may choose to implement the simple payload model in the first instance, and start gathering inputs for the enhanced model where available.

When it comes to the storage models then the main choice here comes down to practicalities. If a provider is unable to record the data access then only the simple storage model can apply. However it seems fairer to try to account for the data access if providers can measure as much, so the enhanced storage model is preferred where practical. Again IRIS may choose a pragmatic approach and implement the simple storage model in the first instance, and start gathering inputs for the enhanced model where available.

5 IRIS NetZero Reporting Requirements

In January 2024 we hosted a meeting at Queen Mary University of London to discuss NetZero carbon reporting in the IRIS context. Thirteen people attended from across IRIS and we considered the requirements from 3 viewpoints: from the end user perspective, from the IRIS resource providers perspective and from the IRIS Federation organisation perspective. Although attendees were predominantly from the IRIS Federation and the IRIS Provider levels we attempted to put ourselves in the shoes of IRIS Users to consider their needs. The discussion was wide ranging across the topic of NetZero and proved valuable input to this report.

5.1 IRIS Federation Reporting Perspectives

The IRIS Federation will need carbon data to report upwards and externally. The Federation will also need carbon data to use to inform decisions its own decisions and to report downwards and internally to providers and users. By having carbon data alongside other accounting data the federation will be well placed to take a lead in the NetZero DRI narrative and help to shape policy in a pragmatic manner.

It was identified that the IRIS federation is likely at a minimum to need the following:

The carbon costs of all IRIS supported activities (providers) broken down into scope 2 and scope 3.

The carbon costs of each IRIS supported project broken down into scope 2 and scope 3.
The notional carbon saved by being a federation, through reduced idle time of equipment.

As well as raw carbon costs some measure of carbon efficiency across platform types and payload types will also be useful to help demonstrate the right mix of platforms (eg, HTC, HPC, GPU, Cloud) and thus that there is value in the heterogeneity across the federation. Data on payload carbon efficiency could also be used to help justify spending on research software engineers/green software engineers by tracking the efficiency improvements they deliver. By collecting data such as energy used per HEPSPEC (CPU benchmark unit) and as a data subset the fossil fuel energy used per HEPSPEC then it is likely that the federation will have more positive data to present while continuing operations. By providing energy or carbon efficiency per well-known benchmark unit then researchers familiar with estimating their future needs in terms of that benchmark unit can easily make reasonable estimates of their future carbon budget requirements.

5.2 IRIS Providers Reporting Perspectives

In the discussions it became apparent that there is a limit on the amount of data that providers can reasonably be expected to collect and report, but there was willingness to engage in an appropriate level of reporting. Providers are often focused on expanding provision to meet the demand for computing resources and so are interested in metrics that can present success while continuing to meet demand. There were concerns that it is not yet known what carbon reporting UKRI will want and that scope 3 figures from vendors may not be easily obtainable

or accurate. There were further concerns about comparisons of carbon cost data from IRIS and that of commercial cloud providers: it is unclear that a direct comparison would be valid.

It was identified that the providers will likely need the following reports:

The total carbon costs of a provider's service broken down by scope.

The breakdown of the above attributing carbon costs to the provider and the users or user groups.

Providers, like the federation, may also be interested in carbon costs that can be shown to be saved by optimising the software run by users.

5.3 IRIS Users Reporting Perspectives

There was concern that providing the wrong metrics to users could drive undesirable user behaviour. Metrics and any level be it federation, provider or user should be appropriate to drive change that is within the legitimate agency of that level. End users cannot choose or change the cooling technology installed at a providers site nor can a provider independently optimise the software that users choose to run. The right people at the right level need to be incentivised to make choices over which they have agency.

Providing users on the scope 2 energy usage of their payload was thought to be the appropriate figure of merit to feedback to users as this most directly relates to the choices and decisions that are within the users ability to control. Converting this to a carbon cost should be done carefully and should probably be done, if at all, using federation wide averages for carbon intensity and possibly also using a federation wide average for PUE.

Alongside this payload energy reporting guidelines on testing payloads and optimising efficiency would also be beneficial for users.

User groups/communities will likely have greater reporting needs, but these are likely aligned with the reporting needs of the federation and provider level, and are assumed to be covered by those requirements, but further user consultation may be needed in future.

6 Outline Delivery Roadmap

6.1 Context

The IRIS Federation operates in the context of UKRI funding and should take account of the context set by UKRI NetZero work. UKRI commissioned a UKRI DRI NetZero Scoping Project of which IRISCAST was part. The scoping project reported⁹ back in August 2023, with 180 recommendations grouped into six strategic themes. UKRI are now moving this forward with an open call¹⁰ closing on 16 April 2024 for a two stage process: Six months for a coordinator to develop a plan for a NetZero DRI Network and then ~3 years to implement that plan by administering a ~£3 million flexible fund for the research community to develop and test new innovative approaches to sustainability and Net Zero.

The IRIS federation operates in the environment outlined above and so should be alert to the opportunities of participating in the NetZero DRI Network and in any event it would be wise for the IRIS federation to align its NetZero work with the larger UKRI NetZero DRI Network efforts and to UK Large Scale Computing initiatives. For example the STFC Sustainability Action Plan 2022-2025 states that STFC “will consider environmental sustainability as part of our large scale and long-term supply contracts and asset procurements” and by the end of financial year 2025 will “Embed sustainability where feasible into our existing procurement contract management procedures” and also “Incorporate emerging understanding on full lifecycle carbon cost into procurement”.

For further context the IRISCAST project reported¹¹ seven findings, which are noted by IRIS-CMP. In summary these IRISCAST findings were:

High level Feedback:

1. Future DRI procurement to include a score based on embedded carbon costs and equipment energy usage.
2. New computer hardware to include energy measurement capability such as IPMI (or per port PDUs) and require the supplier to provide best estimates of embedded carbon costs.
3. Measure energy used by cooling infrastructure and the computing infrastructure.
4. Facilities to keep an inventory of equipment including embedded carbon cost and idle power draw.
5. Monthly (or other periodic) reporting of carbon usage by facilities based on 3 and 4 above. Roll into standard grant reporting regime.

Low Level Feedback:

6. Collect per job (or VM) energy usage by using tools like Slurm (correctly configured). Combined this with embedded carbon from inventory and electricity carbon intensity to feedback job carbon cost to the end user to drive improvements in user code and workflow.
7. Identify user communities and the authors of community codebases so that useful feedback can be given to them to drive the development of more efficient code and workflows.

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8199984>

¹⁰ <https://www.ukri.org/opportunity/net-zero-digital-research-infrastructure-coordinator-and-network/>

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7692451>

6.2 Tackling The NetZero Problem

Figure 4: Diagram showing the key elements of tackling NetZero in the IRIS context.

Figure 4 shows some of the main aspects of tackling NetZero in the IRIS context.

NetZero Computing will require reduction of carbon costs while responding to user demand and ultimately offsetting or capturing the remaining carbon emissions to reach NetZero.

Ignoring offsetting for the time being, this leaves us with the possibilities of reducing the scope 2 costs (reducing operating energy usage) and reducing the scope 3 (embedded) costs.

IRIS providers will need to obtain the scope 3 costs they can from suppliers and manufacturers and fill any gaps using estimates. These scope 3 estimates can then form the basis of a carbon inventory, including buildings and essential infrastructure. The inventory will need to include the lifetime and start-of-life date so that a carbon amortisation rate can be calculated. This scope 3 carbon amortisation rate will be needed to account for the total carbon costs of a payload and also can help to optimise equipment lifetimes.

IRIS will need to focus on reducing energy usage, to address scope 2 carbon costs which leads to a requirement to measure energy usage. This in turn needs us to understand the nuances of real and apparent power usage when calculating energy consumed and resulting carbon emissions. By measuring energy usage of cooling infrastructure and the datacentre energy consumption separately provider sites can get a good understanding of their total energy consumption and the Power Usage Effectiveness (PUE) of their facility. The IRISCAST work showed that providers generally have a poor understanding of their PUE. A

better understanding of the PUE may drive change to improve the cooling efficiency or change to more efficient cooling technology including heat recovery solutions.

Given that the Grid Carbon Intensity varies from season to season and from day to day and even minute to minute, then it has been suggested¹² that timing of computer workloads could be adjusted to minimise their carbon cost. IRIS could periodically review progress in this field of Green Scheduling to see if it proves practical.

Given a good understanding of total energy usage then data from payload allocation systems can be used along with carbon models to apportion energy usage to user payloads and to any idle periods between payloads. The embedded carbon can also be apportioned to payloads but care must be taken in how apportioned costs are communicated to users to avoid motivating unwanted user behaviour.

The payload energy usage can be safely reported directly to users by providers to help drive user code energy optimisation. This may need the provision of new profiling tools and input from Research Software Engineers (RSEs) or Green Software Engineers (GSEs). This begs the question how can the impact of RSEs/GSEs be measured: data about software carbon usage pre and post RSE/GSE intervention could be gathered.

The IRIS federation and providers will want to track site grid carbon intensity and the average off all IRIS providers along with the UK Grid average grid carbon intensity.

Accounting information consisting of aggregate payload data by project and provider idle cost can be passed to an IRIS accounting system. This can produce reports as described in section 5.

If carbon budgets are implemented by UKRI we can expect carbon estimates to go into project proposals which can be informed by the IRIS carbon accounting reports. Proposals can be evaluated, and budgets allocated, then the IRIS carbon accounting system can monitor usage against budget.

Each of these areas start at different levels of maturity and all will need to be developed further on the road to NetZero.

¹² HPC-JEEP Final Report: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7137390>

6.3 IRIS NetZero Actions

Section 6.2 sets out the main issues to be tackled on the route to NetZero. The following table of actions are designed to address the issues raised in the previous section.

It is currently 2024 so a rough timeline to 2030 comprises the following timeframes:

- Now: 2024 to 2026
- Soon: 2026 to 2028
- Later: 2028 to 2030

These timeframes are used in the table below.

ID	Action	By whom	Timeframe
1	Include energy efficiency and scope 3 carbon considerations into procurements with low weighting	Provider	Now
2	Request LCA and scope 3 data from suppliers at procurement	Provider	Now
3	Increase weighting of energy efficiency and scope 3 carbon considerations into procurements	Provider	Soon
4	Require LCA and scope 3 data from suppliers at procurement	Provider	Later
5	Agree a minimum Carbon Inventory schema	Federation	Now
6	Create and maintain the Carbon Inventory	Provider	Now
7	Decide carbon accounting policy for scope 3 write-off/credit if equipment disposed of early or sold as working	Federation	Now
8	Prepare guidelines on how to optimise lifetime of kit for carbon emissions	Federation	Soon
9	Collect Grid Carbon Intensity for: provider sites, federation average and UK average.	Fed/Prov	Now
10	Publish average federation carbon intensity	Federation	Now
11	Share good practice on how real vs apparent AC power measurements effect the processing of different energy use measurements.	Federation	Now
12	Decide on initial carbon model for payload allocation	Federation	Now

ID	Action	By whom	Timeframe
13	Commission an IRIS Carbon Accounting Data Repository: planning and implementation, including data model and data transfer.	Federation	Now
14	Evaluate selected model on payloads daily to give user energy feedback	Provider	Now
15	Evaluate selected model on payloads monthly to report sum of payload energies and idle energy and apportioned embedded carbon costs	Prov/Fed	Now
16	Collect monthly returns of data from providers to IRIS Carbon Accounting Data Repository	Federation	Now
17	Commission reporting portal to provide the identified reports to federation, providers, and users.	Federation	Now
18	Commission reporting to users of payload energy usage and average federation carbon intensity.	Federation	Now
19	Additional tools for user code optimisation such as energy benchmark tools and the addition of profiling queues to services run by providers.	Fed/Prov	Soon
20	Find or commission an energy benchmark for providers to run on compute nodes and keep results in inventory	Federation	Soon
21	Survey GPU energy monitoring frameworks and plan how to add accelerators into carbon monitoring models.	Federation	Soon
22	Review evidence from under-clocking of accelerators and the effect on carbon emissions.	Federation	Soon
23	Collect additional user carbon reporting needs.	Users	Soon
24	Plan how to record and report the impact of Green RSE's.	Federation	Now
25	Regular review of developments in 'Green Scheduling'.	Federation	Now
26	Regular review of UKRU DRI NetZero projects and policy	Federation	Now
27	Bid for UKRI DRI NetZero funds	ALL	Now
28	Prepare IRIS Carbon Costing Framework for grant proposals	Federation	Now

7 Conclusion

In Sections 3 and 4 it has been demonstrated that a simple apportionment model can be used to allocate a service providers energy usage to user payloads and user storage allocations. With the addition of a scope 3 inventory and Grid Carbon Intensity figures it has been shown that both scope 2 and scope 3 Carbon costs could be apportioned to user payloads and storage allocations with the residual being allocated to providers.

An enhanced payload model and enhanced storage model have also been proposed, but both have some drawbacks. The enhanced storage model required measurement of user storage access, which may not be readily available from storage systems deployed at provider facilities. The simple carbon models could be evaluated by both batch and cloud providers with little effort. The enhanced models could probably be evaluated by most providers given moderate effort.

All of the models could be used to motivate both user behaviour and provider operations to become more carbon efficient.

In Sections 5 the carbon reporting requirements of the IRIS Federation, it's service providers, and users were presented and in Section 6 the main issues that will be encountered on the IRIS journey to Net Zero have been discussed and a list of resulting actions that the IRIS Federation may wish to take forwards has been established.

In the short timeframe of this project some practical carbon models have been demonstrated to work on both batch and cloud infrastructures and an outline roadmap to address NetZero within the IRIS Federation has been presented.

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